

The Ocean's role in the 2015 European Heat Wave

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Motivation

- Duchez et al. 2016

Model Set-up

- State of the art coupled climate model, HadGEM3 (GC2):
 - Atmosphere, Ocean, Sea-Ice and Land-Surface Models
- Ocean: NEMO, ORCA025, $\frac{1}{4}^\circ$ horizontal resolution (GO5)
- Atmosphere: UM, N216, approx. $\frac{1}{2}^\circ$ latitude by $\frac{3}{4}^\circ$ longitude (GA6)
- Simulating 1 year requires 1152 cores to compute for 18 hours

Experiment Set-up

- Initialized on May 1st, 2015 from historical+rcp4.5 HadGEM3-GC2
- Climatology is defined as the April/May mean from 1981 to 2010
- 4 different ocean initial conditions through temperature and salinity:

CLIM

Mean 3D T&S from HadGEM3-GC2 from 1981-2010

2015

+ Global
2015 T&S anomaly

Global AM Sea Surface Temperature
2015 - (1981-2010)

NATL

+ North Atlantic only
2015 T&S anomaly

N. Atlantic AM Sea Surface Temperature
2015 - (1981-2010)

NONA

+ No North Atlantic
2015 T&S anomaly

No N. Atlantic AM Sea Surface Temperature
2015 - (1981-2010)

- 3D T&S anomalies taken from NEMO forced run
- 1981-2010 mean soil moisture from historical+rcp4.5 HadGEM3-GC3

Ensemble Set-up

- Ensemble members created by perturbing the SST with a white noise proportional to differences in 5 day means in NEMO forced run
- SST perturbation is applied to ocean surface and tapered towards zero over the upper 50 m
- 30 ensemble members each experiment

Surface Air Temperature

ERA-interim 2015 Anomaly

JJA: 2015-CLIM

Surface Air Temperature

ERA-interim 2015 Anomaly

JJA: 2015-CLIM

DePreSys3

Surface Air Temperature

JJA: NATL-CLIM

JJA: 2015-CLIM

JJA: NONA-CLIM

Surface Air Temperature

JJA: 2015-CLIM

Precipitation

JJA: 2015-CLIM

15 member ensembles

**We choose an arbitrary atmospheric/
sea ice initial condition...**

**Does this choice impact producing a
heatwave over Europe?**

SAT+SIC 2015

2015 Atmosphere

ERA-interim 2015 Anomaly

SAT+SIC 2015

2015 Atmosphere

ERA-interim 2015 Anomaly

1992 Atmosphere

SAT+SIC 2015

2015 Atmosphere

ERA-interim 2015 Anomaly

1992 Atmosphere

1986 Atmosphere

SAT+SIC 1984

2015 Atmosphere

ERA-interim 1984 Anomaly

SAT+SIC 1984

2015 Atmosphere

ERA-interim 1984 Anomaly

1992 Atmosphere

SAT+SIC 1984

2015 Atmosphere

ERA-interim 1984 Anomaly

1992 Atmosphere

1986 Atmosphere

Conclusions

- Initialisation with May 2015 ocean temperatures leads to anomalously warm JJA over Central/Eastern Europe
- Confining SST anomalies to the Atlantic still leads to anomalously warm JJA conditions, but the signal is weaker
- Both atmosphere/sea ice and ocean initial state play an important role in successfully predicting extreme summers
- We are currently investigating the sensitivity of a) atmosphere, b) sea ice or c) soil temperature (already using climatological soil moisture)

Surface Air Temperature 2014

2015 Atmosphere

ERA-interim 1984 Anomaly

1992 Atmosphere

1986 Atmosphere

Surface Air Temperature 1993

2015 Atmosphere

ERA-interim 1984 Anomaly

1992 Atmosphere

1986 Atmosphere

GLOBALMEAN - CLIMMEAN

NATLMEAN - CLIMMEAN

NONAMEAN - CLIMMEAN

ERA-interim 2015 Anomaly

Surface Air Temperature

GLOBMEAN-CLIMMEAN

NATLMEAN-CLIMMEAN

NONAMEAN-CLIMMEAN

95% Significant

Sea Level Pressure

ERA-interim 2015 Anomaly

GLOBMEAN-CLIMMEAN

NATLMEAN-CLIMMEAN

NONAMEAN-CLIMMEAN

95% Significant

Latent Heat Flux

NCEP Reanalysis 2015 Anomaly

GLOBMEAN-CLIMMEAN

NATLMEAN-CLIMMEAN

HadGEM3 JJA SLP
GLOBMEAN - CLIMMEAN

95% Significant

The theoretical response

- Sutton and Mathieu 2002
- Hoskins and Karoly 1981

Figure 9. Schematic illustrating the response of the atmosphere–ocean mixed-layer system to an anomaly in ocean heat-flux convergence (OHFC). The OHFC forcing generates an anomalous air–sea flux exchange, particularly in the form of enhanced evaporation. Convergence in the atmosphere of this heat flux is associated with sensible and latent heating. The steady linear response to the heating is a Low downstream which tilts westwards with height. The anomalous low-level circulation balances the heating over the forcing region and also contributes to the formation of an sea-surface-temperature anomaly downstream. The changes in the time-mean tropospheric structure lead to changes in the transient eddies, but—in our experiment—these have a small effect back on the mean flow.

- An anomaly in OHFC should provoke a high downstream of the cold blob
- The model's high is too much above the cold blob invoking cold northerly winds at its eastern side (over W-Europe)
- The Obs show the high farther to the east than theory predicts and a low over the cold blob
- By Chance? Or did we overlook some other crucial element in the initial conditions?